

Study of Ionization Equilibria of α -(Methylphenylazo)- *p*-Nitrobenzyl Cyanides

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Infrared spectra of α -(methylphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanides indicated that these compounds were with the hydrazone configuration. From the visible spectra it was observed that the ionization equilibria of these compounds were unambiguous unlike that of *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide. The pK' values of these compounds in the mixed aqueous solvents were in the range 10.6-14.5. As the colour change of these compounds with the change in pH was sharp (yellow violet) and was within 1 pH unit, these compounds would be profitably used as acid-base indicators in the determination of both strong and weak acids and bases in water and mixed aqueous media.

DURING the spectrophotometric studies of the ionization equilibria of *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide, a continuous shift in the absorption maxima with a change in pH was observed¹⁻³. It was attributed to the probable anomalous behaviour of the ionization equilibria which might involve the ionization of both the methylene protons⁴ and/or the urge of the nitrosubstituted aromatic ring for the nucleophilic substitution⁵. The weak acid properties of *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide allowed its coupling with diazotized aniline⁶; the product, α -(phenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide did not show any anomalous ionization behaviour⁷. It is thus possible to tailor the series of α -(substituted phenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide for a particular value of ionization constant with a normal behaviour by using the appropriate substituted aniline for diazotization. This paper includes the study of the ionization equilibria of the compounds synthesized by coupling the diazotized toluidines with *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide.

Experimental and Results

A. The literature procedures were used for the preparations of *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (I)⁸ (m.p. 116°-117°) and α -(phenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (II)⁷ (m.p. 201°-202°).

B. *Preparation of α -(methylphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide*: A solution of *o*-toluidine (1.07 g, 10 m moles) in HCl (1 M, 25 ml) was treated at 4° with an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.6 g, 10 m moles) with a vigorous stirring. The mixture was further treated with a cold solution (ca. 4°) of (I) (1.62 g, 10 m moles) in ethanol (100 ml). After 5 min the mixture was kept at room temperature for 30 min. The mixture was filtered and the clear yellow filtrate was cautiously neutralized with NaOH to give a

dark yellow precipitate which on purification on alumina-packed column with benzene-acetone (1 : 1 v/v) gave the orange needles of α -(*o*-methylphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (III) (0.7 g, 26%), m.p. 165°-166° (Found : C, 64.1; H, 4.3; N, 19.6%. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4$ requires C, 64.3; H, 4.3; N, 20.0%).

Diazotization of *m*- and *p*-toluidine and their coupling with (I) by following the procedure given above gave respectively the lemon yellow crystals of α -(*m*-methylphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (IV), (24%, m.p. 180°-181°), and the yellow flakes of α -(*p*-methylphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (V), (31%, m.p. 214°-215°). The chemical analyses of these compounds were comparable with the required analysis for $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4$.

C. *Determination of physical properties*: Infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR 20 and IR 4 spectrophotometers using nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls. Measurements in the visible region were made on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer using a thermostated cuvette holder. A matched pair (10.01 mm) of glass cuvettes was used. Measurements of pH values were made on a Radiometer pH meter $pHM4a$ using G 200 B glass electrode and K 100 calomel electrode. The pH meter was standardized by using 0.05 M aqueous phthalate buffer and was checked with Radiometer buffer type S 1001. Appropriate corrections were applied to the experimental pH values of buffers in mixed aqueous solvent⁹.

A typical experimental data used for the determination of ionization constants is given in Table I (Fig. 1). The apparent values of ionization constants of compounds III, IV and V, pK' , in the mixed aqueous solvents were determined by using the relation¹⁰.

$$pK' = pH + \log \frac{A_I - A}{A - A_M}$$

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TABLE 1—IONIZATION CONSTANT OF α -(*o*-METHYLPHENYLAZO)-*p*-NITROBENZYL CYANIDE

Solvent : 70.08 weight percent, methanol-water
 Concentration : $3.571 \times 10^{-5} M$. Ionic strength : 0.05
 Temperature, $25^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ Analytical wavelength : 560nm
 Absorbance due to molecular species = $A_M = 0.000$
 Absorbance due to ionic species = $A_I = 1.07$

pH	A	$A_I - A$	$A - A_M$	$\log \frac{A_I - A}{A - A_M}$	pK'	Mean value of pK'
10.81	0.217	0.853	0.217	0.5944	11.40	11.37 \pm 0.06
10.94	0.319	0.751	0.319	0.3718	11.31	
11.15	0.417	0.652	0.417	0.1948	11.35	
11.32	0.507	0.563	0.507	0.0455	11.37	
11.53	0.623	0.447	0.623	1.8558	11.38	
11.73	0.727	0.343	0.727	1.6738	11.40	

where A_I is the absorbance of the ionic form, A_M is the absorbance of the molecular form and A is the absorbance at the intermediate known pH, all measured at the identical total indicator concentration

Infrared spectra of compounds II-V showed a definite strong band in the region $3260-3230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which was assigned to N-H stretching mode of vibration^{13,14}. Infrared spectra of compound I showed a medium intensity band at 2880 cm^{-1} which was assigned to C-H attached to the groups like -CN, -C = O^{15,16}. Infrared spectra of compounds II-V did not show any band in the region $2920-2840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus the hydrazone configuration was indicated for compounds II-V.

A comparison of the spectra of compounds I-V with that of 4-phenylazo-1-naphthol¹⁷ indicated that the strong bands observed in the regions $1560-1545 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1265-1260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for compounds II-V were associated with a combined vibrational mode involving the NH bending and some skeletal stretching motion and with NH bending mode respectively. A low frequency strong band observed in the region $755-750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed for compounds II-V was assigned to RNO₂ deformation¹⁸.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of α -(*o*-methylphenylazo)-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide ($3.571 \times 10^{-5} M$) in 70.08 wt. percent methanol-water mixture.

and at the same wavelength. It was possible to measure A_I and A_M at the absorption maxima by using the solutions of fairly high and low pH values respectively.

A summary of the absorption spectra and ionization constants of indicators III, IV and V in methanol-water and ethanol-water mixtures is given in Table 2.

Discussion

1. Infrared spectra

The indicators II to V may have either a hydrazone (i) or an azo (ii) configuration¹¹⁻¹².

2. Ionization constants

The absorption spectra showed (Fig. 1) a characteristic isobestic point for the solutions of indicator III in the pH range 7.2 to 13.5. Thus mainly one equilibrium was present. A similar behaviour was observed for IV and V.

A comparison of the ionization constants in ethanol-water and methanol-water mixtures with the comparable weight percentages decisively indicated the influence of the basicity of solvent. Ethanol being more basic, the ionization constants were higher in ethanol than those in methanol.

TABLE 2—IONIZATION CONSTANTS OF α -(METHYLPHENYLAZO)-*p*-NITROBENZYL CYANIDES

Temperature, 25.0° ± 0.2°		Ionic strength, 0.05						
Compound	Solvent, weight per cent	*Dielectric constant <i>D</i>	Molecule		Anion		Isosbestic point nm	pK'
			Absorption maxima	Molar absorptions × 10 ⁻⁴	Absorption maxima	Molar absorptions × 10 ⁻⁴		
III. Methanol-Water								
	70.08	47.0	419	2.403	560	2.996	462	11.37 ± 0.06
	43.83	59.0	418	2.044	560	2.745	460	11.22 ± 0.04
	20.12	69.6	426	1.940	554	2.576	462	12.55 ± 0.04
Ethanol-Water								
	70.27	37.4	417	2.576	562	3.920	471	11.13 ± 0.02
	44.09	52.2	416	2.330	562	3.360	465	11.05 ± 0.05
	20.40	66.9	421	2.196	557	2.380	470	11.75 ± 0.02
Water								
		78.3						14.10**
IV. Methanol-Water								
	70.08	47.0	418	2.996	559	30.024	460	11.45 ± 0.06
	43.83	59.0	414	2.576	563	2.996	462	10.60 ± 0.04
	20.12	69.6	424	1.204	554	2.380	466	12.26 ± 0.04
Ethanol-Water								
	70.27	37.4	416	2.296	563	3.207	464	10.92 ± 0.04
	44.09	52.2	414	2.276	563	3.248	466	10.60 ± 0.05
	20.40	66.9	420	0.952	558	2.884	460	11.67 ± 0.05
Water								
		78.3						14.05**
V. Methanol-Water								
	70.08	47.0	413	2.492	560	3.024	462	11.48 ± 0.06
	43.83	59.0	417	2.296	561	2.716	465	11.10 ± 0.03
	20.12	69.6	425	2.013	552	2.425	465	12.37 ± 0.06
Ethanol-Water								
	70.27	37.4	417	2.353	560	2.923	462	11.20 ± 0.04
	44.09	52.2	416	2.408	562	3.221	464	11.00 ± 0.04
	20.40	66.9	422	1.148	556	2.520	465	11.90 ± 0.05
Water								
		78.3						14.50**

* J. Timmermans, 'Physicochemical Constants of Binary Systems', Vol. IV, Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 168, 202.

** Values determined by graphical extrapolation.

Two major factors contribute to the solvent effect on the ionization constants—the bulk properties of the medium¹⁹, and the short range intermolecular forces. The bulk properties include the dielectric constant of the medium; however, it is known that the microscopic dielectric constant plays an important role²⁰. If the effect of dielectric constant of the two constituents of mixed media on the ionization constant were additive, a linear plot would be expected for ionization constants vs dielectric constant. However, the typical hockey-stick-type curves were obtained. This behaviour indicated that at least two different factors were operating in the reverse directions on the ionization equilibria. The ionization involves the separation of the charged species and the work required for the separation of the two charged species will be minimum for a medium of high dielectric constant. The solvation of the charged species will be very different from that of the parent neutral molecule. When the effect of the dielectric constant of the medium is only considered, the ionization of N-H group will decrease when the solvent is changed from water to organic solvents (like ethanol), while the specific intermolecular interactions will favour the ionization in organic

solvents (like ethanol) over that in water. The overall effect will be that the two effects influencing ionization will compensate each other at a particular solvent composition to give the extremal value of ionization constant. This value corresponds to the minimum observed in the curve of pK' vs solvent composition.

The anomalous nature of ionization of *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide is not observed in the azo dyes reported in this work. The indicators can have a large range of pK' values depending on the substituents. These compounds are soluble in alcohol-water mixtures and are stable even in media of high pH values. The ionic forms of the indicators are dark coloured and the absorbance values in the media of high pH values show a linear relation with pH. These properties suggest that the azo dyes reported in the present work are suitable for the measurements of high pH values in alcohol-water mixtures.

The colour change (yellow → violet) associated with the ionization is sharp and is within one pH unit. One proton from salicylic- and benzoic acids, two protons from tartaric-, sulphosalicylic-, phthalic-,

Fig. 2. Variation of pK' with dielectric constant (D) of the solvent medium.
 ● Ethanol water, ○ Methanol water, □ water.

oxalic-, orthophosphoric acids, and three protons from citric acid are very well titrated; the titration of one mole proton from the salts like NaH_2PO_4 and $KHSO_4$ can also be carried out by using these indicators. As the molar absorptivities of these indicators are high (Table 2), the quantity of the indicator required for the observable colour change during the acid-base titrations is small; the indicator error is less than 0.02 ml of 0.05 M NaOH (for three drops of 0.1% indicator) for most of the titrations. The indicator solutions have good keeping quality; the solutions of indicator stored under the normal conditions for more than a year showed less than 2% change in absorbance.

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